

LOCALIZED APPETIZER AND DESSERTS IN ENHANCING THE COOKERY SKILLS OF GRADE 9 STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Food does not only provide the purpose of sustaining the needs of the human body rather, it is also a way of knowing the culture, climate, and inclinations in a certain locality and its people. In the province of Quezon, the preparation and cooking of food from ingredients present in the locality further shows the place's distinct historical and cultural practices. However, as time passed by there is an evident change in the dietary patterns of the people in the municipality of San Antonio, Quezon. People chose to eat food that are from fast food restaurants, convenience food products, and highly processed food wherein, this clearly shows that the practice of cooking at home is constantly decreasing. Hence the purpose of this study is to of carry out a comprehensive study in order to assess the cookery skills among the Grade 9 students of Juanito C. Wagan National High School S.Y: 2020 – 2021. This paper assessed the perception of the student's responding on the localized appetizer and dessert recipe that they possessed in terms of Selection with the overall mean of 3.80, Organization gained an overall mean of 3.82, Interpretations' overall mean is 3.81, Ingredients with the overall mean of 3.85, Methods of preparation gained an overall mean of 3.82 and Nutritive Profile overall mean is 3.87 and the learners cooking skills in terms of Personal Entrepreneurial with an overall mean of 3.78, Technical and Mechanical having an overall mean of 3.75, and Creative and Organizational overall mean of 3.76 . Based form the result of this study, there is a significant relationship between all the variables given between the localized appetizer and desserts and the cooking skills of the learners and there is a direct relationship between the localized appetizer and desserts and cooking skills as taken to the responses of the learner respondents. Thus, it has been concluded that the hypotheses presented in this study were not supported by evidence and therefore. With this, it is recommended that educators may train their students the cooking skills, plan for future growth, and appreciate the importance of cooking skills that will enable the people to remember the locality's culture in cooking. With the limited resources the schools may not be able to provide all the necessary things for young student aspirants for their training to gain skills towards cooking, it is proposed that the teachers may ask support in giving enough resources for the learners and may be given training that will enhance their cooking skills.

Keywords: Cookery Skills, Cultural Practices, Food, Historical, Locality